

Fertility Europe & B2-InF: A powerful synergy.

Anita Fincham
Manager at Fertility Europe.

Fertility Europe is the umbrella association for infertility patients, which includes solely patient representatives: *“We are all pretty much people with the experience of infertility”*, - says **Anita Fincham**, manager at Fertility Europe. This means that just as most patient associations, it is **mainly run by volunteers who are fueled by passion and firm intention** but often lack the know-how when it comes to running such an organization. This has turned into a strength pushing them to help each other so that **for each new member, it gets easier and easier to be more efficient and carry out activities properly**: *“The new volunteers no longer have to waste time trying to reinvent the wheel”*.

They are **primarily interested in supporting and promoting the best access to fertility treatment in Europe**. However, at the same time, they would like to address the other side of the spectrum, such as **introducing fertility education in schools and everyday life to prevent young people from encountering related issues later in their lives**. Fertility Europe also works to educate medical staff on how to convey information about fertility and reproductive health to patients at different stages of life to make sure those wrong assumptions are not made. Everyone must have the best chances to become parents if it is something they wish for.

Many countries with meagre birth rates still do not adequately address the problem for various reasons. One of which is that the intricate web of meanings associated with fertility makes communication about the topic very complex for governments. *“There are many traps to this communication”*, - explains Anita Fincham, as history shows that governments who try communicating about fertility are often associated with traditionalist, anti-feminist parties by the general public. **The responsibility to disseminate information, educate the young and help those who are already facing problems falls upon other organizations such as B2-InF and Fertility Europe**. *“Going back to an old-school mindset of family planning is never our intention. We just want to arm the young with the knowledge and tools to make their own choices fully aware of their limitations”*.

Therefore, it is clear that the goals and purpose of Fertility Europe and B2-InF are aligned and fundamentally **intertwined in their pursuit of an improved and standardized fertility journey**. Dr. Güell, the B2-inF’s coordinator, is worried about the ambiguous information that ART services are giving to the population about infertility. *“The needs of the patients are not always put first as they should be”*, he said. In this sense, the young population needs to be better informed about fertility, and understand their own body: *“To study the causes of infertility and trying to restore fertility must be the first steps, both from a health and economic point of view”*, concludes Dr. Güell.

Fertility Europe was pleased to join this project and fully supports collecting accurate data among young adults. This specific group of people is crucial in the fight against infertility, who are also still in time to make real-life changes. Mrs. Fincham highlights how important it is for all organizations and institutions specialized in the field to support each other, creating consistent **synergies that will open conversations at the European level leading to real change**.

All in all, B2-InF and Fertility Europe are there where policymakers fail.